

Effective home literacy practices experienced by selected senior high school students in English subjects

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Abstract

This qualitative research project is a case study to find effective home literacy practices in English subjects experienced by the selected Landy National High School learners. This is to foster parent involvement and best support students' literacy development. Learners require rich home literacy practices where the participation of parents engages in effective literacy practices. The case study was proposed and conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic, which changed the quality of the participant's home literacy practices and the researcher's ability to engage with study participants fully. The home literacy practices were typically seen during face-to-face home visitation for observation and interviews. Although the study is being proposed to the parents and the participants, it is often difficult to support the learners' full engagement in the content and the parents' opinions towards their children's study habits. Most learners say they study independently and seek help once needed, even if they can work most of the time on their own. The researcher found that reading is one of the most effective home literacy practices during distance learning. Despite lacking reading materials, most participants seek ways to support their eagerness to learn and read.

Keywords: Best practices; home literacy practices; language development; literacy development; reading.

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To cite this article:

Linga, J. L., & Decena, A. J. (2023). Effective home literacy practices experienced by selected senior high school students in English subjects. *SDCA Asia-Pacific Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 5(1), 52-59.

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8031356

Introduction

It is widely recognized that home literacy plays a crucial role in language and literacy development skills, especially in the 21st century (Shoghi et al., 2013). However, existing research primarily focuses on 1st world countries with moderate to high-income populations, leaving a gap in our understanding of the family-related factors that affect senior high school learners' home literacy skills in the Philippines. In response to this gap, this study aims to investigate the impact of parental assistance and involvement on home literacy skills, specifically in the context of modular learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Previous studies have shed light on the positive relationship between home literacy practices and academic achievement among senior high school students. For instance, Wang (2014) examined home literacy practices in Taiwan and found that they had a positive effect on academic achievement. Similarly, Khajehpour and Ghazvini (2011) explored parental involvement in literacy practices among high school students and discovered a positive impact on literacy achievement. These studies emphasize the significance of parental involvement in cognitive development and academic success.

Family Literacy Theory encompasses various theories that highlight the crucial role of families in shaping children's literacy skills and emphasize the importance of collaboration between families and educators (Reybok, 2022). Specifically, the following family literacy theories are relevant to our study:

Ecological Systems Theory proposed by Urie Bronfenbrenner, emphasizes the interconnectedness of various environments in a child's life, including the family, school, and community. It recognizes that the family environment plays a central role in supporting children's literacy development and emphasizes the need for collaboration between families and other ecological systems to promote literacy skills.

Socio-Cultural Theory developed by Lev Vygotsky, posits that children's learning and development are shaped by social interactions and cultural contexts. Within the family, parents and caregivers serve as important mediators of literacy practices and provide guidance and support for children's literacy learning.

Transactional Theory of Reading and Writing proposed by Louise Rosenblatt, emphasizes the dynamic interaction between readers, writers, and texts. It recognizes that reading and writing are active processes influenced by individual experiences, interpretations, and social contexts. Within the family setting, this theory highlights the importance of engaging children in meaningful reading and writing experiences.

The lack of parental involvement in children's literacy development and the absence of effective communication and opportunities for families to establish a functional home literacy environment are significant challenges. Schools often fail to engage parents adequately, resulting in students' weak written and oral communication skills, which hinder their academic success and information access across subjects. Thus, this study aims to identify efficient and effective ways to promote children's reading and language skills, thereby alleviating these challenges.

By considering these family literacy theories, our study aims to explore the impact of parental involvement on the home literacy skills of senior high school learners in the Philippines, particularly within the context of modular learning. The researchers investigated the extent of parental assistance and involvement in their children's education and examined how these factors relate to the development of reading and writing abilities (Alhabeeb, 2016). This research would provide valuable insights into the role of family literacy practices and contribute to the understanding of effective strategies for promoting literacy outcomes in similar contexts (Blischak et al., 2003). By examining the factors contributing to successful home literacy practices in a low to middle-income context, this study can provide valuable insights for policymakers and educators to enhance literacy outcomes in similar settings (Marcella et al., 2014). This research reviewed the relationship between parental involvement and children's literacy development, described the methodology employed, presented the results, and discussed their implications for future research and practice in literacy education.

The researchers believe that identifying successful home literacy practices can benefit students, their parents, instructors, school officials, and future researchers. Strong literacy skills are necessary for students to succeed academically, making it essential for instructors to identify their strengths and weaknesses to provide tailored instruction. Parents can better support their children's literacy development by understanding successful home literacy practices. The study's findings may also help school administrators create a school-wide plan to clarify parent involvement and increase reading achievement at the school and district levels. Finally, the study's findings can be a reference for future researchers to delve deeper into other aspects of home literacy practices. The study aimed to document and to verify the selected learners' home literacy programs. The researchers did not initially interact with the students or their parents but instead focused on observing and listening to their family interactions and learning strategies.

To address these issues, the following questions will guide the research:

Main Problem: What effective home literacy practices in English subjects were experienced by the selected learners from Landy National High School?

Sub Problems:

1. What are the home literacy practices of the selected students?
2. What are the challenges experienced by the selected students in having an effective home literacy practice in English subjects?

3. How do parents assist children's literacy development at home?
4. How does parent involvement in student achievement affect the effective home literacy activities in English subjects for their literacy development?
5. What intervention program design for effective home literacy practices for SHS students in English subjects can be proposed based on the results of the study?

The study uses the input-process-output (IPO) research paradigm to examine the impact of various factors on home literacy practices and children's literacy development. The input of the paradigm includes factors that affect home literacy practices, such as the nature of literacy activities at home and the level of parental support for literacy development (Poolman et al., 2017). The process involves analyzing these factors, including the types of literacy activities in the house and parents' challenges in supporting literacy development. The output of the study is an intervention program aimed at improving home literacy practices for senior high school students in English subjects. The intervention program includes strategies, such as reading comprehension exercises and vocabulary-building activities, to enhance students' language skills and academic performance. The study's outcome is the impact of effective home literacy practices on children's literacy development. Through this case study, the researcher aims to identify effective home literacy practices and help families who struggle to maintain successful learning practices at home.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically utilizing a case study approach, to explore the home literacy practices of senior high school students in English subjects within a single institution. The study spanned four months, from August 2022 to November 2022. The study used a qualitative case study on ten participants from Landy National High School in Landy, Santa Cruz, Marinduque, Philippines. The researchers observed and verified the home literacy programs of five students and five parents through direct observation of their day-to-day learning activities at home.

Data collection involved several methods, including semi-structured interviews, observations, and document analysis. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with five selected parents and five learners to gather information on their home literacy practices, available resources, challenges faced, and parental support. Observations were conducted in the learners' home environments, focusing on their study areas, to capture various aspects of their literacy practices, such as materials used, frequency of reading and writing activities, and parental support. Document analysis was carried out to assess the learners' academic performance in English subjects, specifically in areas like English for Academic and Professional Purposes, Reading and Writing, and Creative Writing for Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and HUMSS tracks, respectively.

Thematic analysis was employed for data analysis. The researcher transcribed interviews and observations and identified themes from the data. The data were then analyzed through coding and organizing the codes into themes.

The chosen qualitative research design, specifically the case study approach, and the selected data collection methods of semi-structured interviews, observations, and document analysis allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the home literacy practices of senior high school students in English subjects. These methods facilitated in-depth exploration and analysis of the participants' experiences.

The researcher employed semi-structured interviews to obtain open-ended responses and flexibility in exploring pertinent topics related to participants' literacy routines. Personal interviews fostered direct engagement with participants, establishing rapport and gathering detailed information. Observations and gathering of materials aided in identifying recurring patterns and motifs in participants' literacy practices. The researcher ensured ethical considerations by seeking permission from the school head, obtaining informed consent from participants, maintaining confidentiality and privacy, and conducting immediate analysis and evaluation of data. The observations were conducted over four days with each family, observing five families outside of school, and interviews with parents and target learners were conducted afterward. Digital resources were also utilized to support the literacy development of senior high school students, providing access to reading materials, online writing opportunities, and feedback. These practices aimed to engage participants with challenging and meaningful literacy materials and foster critical reading and analytical writing skills.

The use of these specific instruments and data collection procedures was well-suited to address the research questions and goals. They allowed for the collection of rich and comprehensive data on the participants' at-home literacy practices and experiences. Furthermore, the researcher adhered to ethical considerations, including seeking permission, obtaining consent, maintaining confidentiality, and ensuring objective analysis and evaluation of the data to uphold reliability and validity.

In addition to the aforementioned instruments, the researcher implemented effective practices to support the literacy development of senior high school students. This included providing digital reading materials, online writing opportunities, and individual feedback. These practices were particularly valuable in the context of distance learning, aiding students in engaging with challenging and meaningful literacy materials and cultivating critical reading and analytical writing skills. By utilizing appropriate instruments, data collection procedures, and effective practices to support literacy development, the researcher obtained comprehensive data and generated valuable insights into the participants' at-home literacy practices and experiences.

Results and Discussion

During the one-hour in-depth interview, the researcher covered various topics related to the student's home literacy practices in English subjects, such as reading books, writing essays, and engaging in discussions. By exploring these activities in detail, the researcher identified key themes and patterns in the students' literacy practices that could inform future research and interventions.

The study provides valuable insights into the home literacy practices of senior high school students in English topics. It highlights the importance of in-depth interviews to gain a more detailed and nuanced understanding of participants' experiences and practices. The findings of this study have implications for educational policy and practice, as well as future research in this area.

Table 1. Home Literacy Practices of Learners

Essential Themes	Categories	Thematic Statements
Reading from different resources	Home support	L1: <i>I have time to read after my household chores since I must take good care of my two children.</i> L2: <i>My mother ensures that all my books are appropriately arranged and must be returned to where I get them.</i>
	Peer support	L3: <i>I ensure I will lend time to read after church duty or in my free time.</i>
Independent learning	Importance of reading materials	L5: <i>I feel the materials are still needed for the sake of reading.</i>
	Perseverance	L3: <i>Most of the time, my teacher serves as the guide for our task.</i> L2: <i>I usually work on my school tasks alone since I cannot ask my parents about my lessons.</i>
	School Support	L3: <i>I believe that teachers significantly influence how they will be motivated to read.</i>
	Relying on the internet	L1: <i>I think technology takes the place of books.</i>
	Peer support system	L4: <i>After the pandemic and being part of the learner who attended limited face-to-face classes, I worked on my performance task with the assistance of my friends.</i>

Legend: L1: Learner 1, L2: Learner 2, L3: Learner 3, L4: Learner 4, L5: Learner 5

Table 1 presents the essential themes and categories from the data collected during the interviews. The majority of respondents' statements showed that some rely heavily on their teacher for guidance on school tasks. In contrast, others believe that technology is replacing books as a means of learning and reading. Meanwhile, some participants experienced limited face-to-face classes due to the pandemic and had to rely on assistance from friends to complete their performance tasks.

The data suggest a relationship between home literacy practices and emergent literacy skills, a critical aspect of early childhood development. This emphasizes the importance of fostering a reading culture at home to support children's literacy development (Neha & Rule, 2018). The study's findings also highlighted the importance of literacy motivation in shaping learners' emergent literacy skills and how parents and caregivers play a crucial role in shaping learners' early literacy experiences and, consequently, their motivation to learn.

The study's results underscore the need for parents and caregivers to create a supportive and engaging language and literacy environment for their children. Educators can incorporate culturally relevant and exciting literacy activities into their instructional strategies. By working together, parents, caregivers, and educators can help create a strong foundation for learners' academic and personal success.

Educators can support learners' language and literacy development and promote learning motivation by incorporating culturally relevant and engaging literacy activities into their instructional practices. Overall, this qualitative case study provided valuable insights into the home literacy practices of senior high school students in English topics. Through the use of in-depth interviews, the researcher was able to gain a deeper understanding of the literacy practices of these students and identify important themes and patterns. The study highlighted the importance of fostering a positive and supportive language and literacy environment at home to support children's literacy development and promote their learning motivation.

These findings have important implications for educational policy and practice. Educators and parents can use this information to inform curriculum development, instructional strategies, and home literacy practices that foster literacy motivation and support the development of emergent literacy skills in learners (Mkhize, 2016). By working together, parents, caregivers, and educators can help create a strong foundation for learners' academic and personal success (Thomas et al., 2021).

The respondents' continued reliance on books for reference and their dedication to organizing and caring for their reading materials is a testament to the enduring value of books in the digital age. This finding is consistent with a 2016 study conducted by the Pew Research Center, which aimed to understand American adults' reading habits and preferences in the digital age. The survey found that print books remain the most popular format for reading, with 65% of Americans reporting having read a print book in the past year, while only 28% reported reading an e-book (Perrin, 2016).

Despite limited space at home, the respondents recognized the importance of reading and prioritized it by keeping their books adequately labeled and categorized. Their efforts to maintain and collect books show that they believe books are crucial to their education and personal growth. Furthermore, the respondents' recognition of books' role in enhancing reading comprehension highlights the significant impact books can have on learners (Maharsi et al., 2019).

One respondent's resourcefulness in caring for his books and acquiring additional materials from classmates indicates a deep appreciation for the value of reading, even without a dedicated bookshelf. This finding suggests that a lack of access to reading materials should not necessarily impede a child's love for learning as long as there is a genuine interest in expanding one's knowledge beyond what is readily available. These findings underscore literacy's critical role in a person's development and the need for communities to support and encourage reading by providing access to a wide range of reading materials, including libraries, digital resources, and other reading materials (Bitetti & Hammer, 2016).

The study also emphasizes that the ability to learn independently varies among students and individuals. While some may naturally be inclined towards independent learning, others may require more teacher guidance and support. Age and maturity also play a significant role in the degree to which students depend on their teachers. Independent learning is not synonymous with learning alone. Teachers play a vital role in fostering independent understanding by providing opportunities for self-directed education and offering guidance and support when necessary.

The respondents' statements showed how children primarily taught by teachers could start acquiring the abilities needed for independent study. By supporting students' development of these qualities, teachers can help students become more self-reliant and responsible in both the classroom and life. This highlights the importance of supporting students in developing the skills and qualities necessary for independent study.

Teachers play a critical role in helping students become more self-reliant and responsible, both in the classroom and life. By fostering critical thinking, problem-solving, and time management skills, teachers can help students become more self-directed and independent learners. It is important to note that developing independent study skills is not something that happens overnight. It is a process that requires ongoing support and guidance from teachers.

Teachers can provide this support by creating a supportive and engaging learning environment, providing opportunities for student-led inquiry and project-based learning, and offering feedback and encouragement throughout the learning process. By fostering the skills and qualities necessary for independent study, teachers can help students become more self-reliant and responsible in both the classroom and in life.

Table 2. Challenges they encounter by the learners in creating a literacy-rich home environment

Categories	Thematic Statements
Time management	<i>I make sure that I manage my time as a mother and as a student.</i>
Resources	<i>Since references are significant, especially during the pandemic, I look for my old books and notes.</i>
Learning spaces	<i>Being a church helper, it is difficult to use my spare time to read, but I use ample time to cope with the lessons, especially for my performance tasks.</i> <i>Set up space outside to do my task without being disturbed by siblings.</i> <i>I provided a space where my child could read and study.</i>

Table 2, as presented in the study, shows the challenges encountered by respondents in creating a literacy-rich home environment. The data gathered suggests that despite daily disruptions and challenges, the respondents prioritize their and their children's education. Time management is crucial to balancing responsibilities as a mother and as a student. The value of having relevant resources, such as old books and notes, is emphasized, especially during crises like the pandemic. Respondents actively engage in multiple activities but try to allocate ample time for studying. Setting up a space conducive to researching and providing a designated area for children to learn are steps taken by respondents to create a supportive environment.

These statements highlight the importance of prioritizing education and taking proactive steps to overcome obstacles to achieve academic goals. The study supports the importance of parental involvement in creating a supportive home environment and fostering independent learning. A literacy-rich environment promotes literacy-based activities that help children explore and interact with text in various ways, increasing confidence, competence, and success in academic and personal pursuits.

The study's findings underscore the significance of creating a supportive environment that encourages learning, especially during crises like the pandemic. Time management, relevant resources, designated learning spaces, and a literacy-rich environment are crucial to achieving academic success. Parents play an essential role in fostering independent learning and supporting their children's educational goals. The study highlights the importance of recognizing these elements to create a supportive environment that fosters academic success (Dixon & Wu, 2014).

Table 3. The assistance of parents towards children's literacy practices

Categories	Thematic Statements
Working	<i>My parents / relatives are busy with their work.</i>
No idea	<i>Others hesitate to help since they don't know about the lesson.</i>
Information from others	<i>I asked my elder siblings since they had already finished the subject.</i>

Table 3 displays the challenges faced by the respondents in their literacy practices due to insufficient parental assistance. Some respondents mention that their parents or relatives are busy with work, which results in their inability to seek help or guidance. Others hesitate to help since they may not be familiar with the lesson or subject matter. However, some resourceful respondents turn to their elder siblings, who have completed the same subject, for help.

The data gathered from the study highlights the importance of regular interactions between parents and their children about learning, especially in the context of working parents. The study reveals that parental involvement in their children's education is crucial for academic success, and regular communication about learning can help bridge the gap between home and school. This is supported by the research of Jeynes (2005), which shows that parental involvement in their children's education is linked to higher levels of academic achievement, with the most substantial effects seen in low-income and minority students.

Furthermore, the study highlights that a shortage of learning materials can significantly impede children's academic attainment. This underscores the importance of providing children with the necessary resources to succeed, which can be challenging for families with lower socioeconomic levels that may experience material hardship.

The statement also emphasizes the negative impact of financial stress on parental involvement in their children's education. Parent's ability to provide support and resources may be compromised by financial difficulties, resulting in decreased involvement with their children. However, despite these challenges, the statement underscores the positive effects that involved parents can have on their children's academic success, regardless of their financial situation.

The participants' responses revealed that many face the challenge of limited parental assistance, primarily due to their parents' work schedules. Nonetheless, the respondents demonstrate resourcefulness and determination to find a solution to their problems. This reinforces the critical role of parental involvement in their children's education and highlights the positive impact that involved parents can have on their children's academic success.

The participants also highlighted the importance of teacher involvement in their learning, with some respondents asking their teacher for guidance when their parents are unavailable. This further emphasizes the need for collaboration between parents and teachers to support children's academic success.

The study underscores the critical role of parental involvement in their children's education, the importance of providing adequate learning resources, and the challenges families with lower socioeconomic levels face. Nonetheless, the statement underscores the positive impact that involved parents can have on their children's academic success, regardless of their financial situation. Finally, the participants' responses reveal the importance of teacher involvement in supporting children's academic success.

Table 4. Parents' involvement in effective home literacy practices

Categories	Thematic Statements
Support	<i>I have strong support from my relatives /family.</i> <i>I always ensure that I will never miss any single event of my child during school events.</i>
Assistance	<i>I seek help or assistance from others, especially my brothers and sisters.</i>
Belongingness	<i>Adult learners help their younger siblings.</i> <i>Since I am living with my own family, most of the time, my husband helps me to accomplish my work.</i> <i>My parents keep on updating my school standing.</i>
Constant Communication	<i>As a parent, I ensure constant communication with the school.</i>

Table 4 presents the results of the parent's involvement in effective home literacy practices and the thematic statements under each category. The responses indicate that family support and participation play a critical role in learners' academic success, with parents and siblings offering assistance and support as needed. The importance of spousal support is also highlighted in the responses, with some respondents mentioning that their partners help them with their work and attend school events.

The data also suggests constant communication between parents and schools is vital for learners' academic success. Respondents mentioned the importance of attending school events, parent-teacher conferences and keeping updated on their child's school standing. Effective communication between parents, teachers, and schools is necessary to identify and address issues or concerns hindering the student's development and love for learning.

Overall, the results emphasize the importance of creating a supportive and welcoming learning environment at home and school, where parents and teachers work together to provide learners with the necessary resources and support to achieve their educational aspirations. Effective communication and involvement of family members are essential in helping learners succeed academically, and it is required to continue fostering this partnership to advance every child's education (Epstein & Sheldon, 2018).

The study aimed to design an intervention program to improve Senior High School (SHS) students' literacy skills in English through effective home literacy practices. Like other schools in the Philippines, Landy National High School has adopted modular learning as a mode of education delivery due to the pandemic. This shift presents challenges to students, particularly in their literacy skills. The intervention program, called the Home Literacy Initiative, aims to address this gap by providing support and resources to SHS students and their families in developing effective home literacy practices.

The intervention program consists of three phases: planning, implementation, and evaluation. In the planning phase, a needs assessment was conducted to determine the students' literacy skills in English and identify specific areas needing support. The intervention design and activities were formulated based on the needs assessment results, and materials and resources such as modules, guides, and activities were developed. The stakeholders involved in the intervention program, such as school administrators, teachers, parents, and students, were identified.

The program's objectives, activities, and resources were presented to the school administrators, teachers, parents, and students through orientation and training sessions in the implementation phase. The home literacy modules and activities were then distributed to the students, along with guidelines for the parents to facilitate the exercises at home. Teachers conducted follow-up activities and remediation sessions to monitor the student's progress and provide support as needed. Workshops or seminars for parents were instructed to provide them with strategies and techniques to support their children's English literacy development.

The evaluation phase included formative and summative evaluations to assess the program's effectiveness in improving the students' English literacy skills and increasing parent involvement. The evaluation results were used to enhance the program's design and activities for future implementation, and the stakeholders were informed of the results to promote transparency and accountability.

Overall, the Home Literacy Initiative addresses SHS students' challenges in English literacy development by providing them and their families with the necessary support and resources. The program's implementation and evaluation phases aim to ensure its effectiveness in meeting its objectives and improving the students' English literacy skills.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings and evaluation of the study, it is evident that educational policies and practices can be strengthened by improving the school, teacher, and parent relationship regarding their child's development, with a specific focus on increasing parental knowledge of language and literacy development. This necessitates expanding the scope of parent interaction beyond the typical school-home relationship and involving parents in all stages of their child's development. Such efforts can encourage students to persevere and work independently, knowing that their parents support their academic pursuits. This highlights the significance of involving parents in their child's education and the need to broaden their contributions to their child's learning experience.

By doing so, educational policies and practices can be enhanced, leading to a more supportive and nurturing learning environment for students (Castro et al., 2015; Tang et al., 2020). The study also identified reading as one of the most beneficial home literacy activities for participants. Additionally, it found that support from parents and older siblings plays a crucial role in promoting good literacy practices at home. Despite having various exercises, participants were able to concentrate on academic tasks. Therefore, parents should be mindful of their time spent helping their children with activities like reading and creating a comfortable study area at home. These efforts can contribute to a child's academic success (Juel, 1988).

Furthermore, parents play a crucial role in promoting and developing their child's reading skills, which can have a positive impact on their academic and professional success in the future. Parents should understand that the level of encouragement and guidance they provide significantly influences their child's reading ability and their ability to manage large amounts of information. It is important for parents to recognize that the extent to which their child can read is related to the degree to which they have encouraged them to read. By developing a more disciplined reading routine, children can progress from passive reading to more critical tasks that require deeper thinking. Children have a natural inclination to analyze and evaluate the information they encounter, and this ability can be nurtured into excellent writing skills with the right opportunities (Landry & Smith, 2006; Marôco, 2021).

The successful engagement of families, schools, and communities is crucial in supporting students' educational journeys. Parental engagement programs and initiatives that understand this relationship and the broader context of a child's development are essential. It requires joint efforts from all parties to help students reach their full potential (Epstein & Sheldon, 2018; Henderson & Mapp, 2002).

To further enhance the home literacy skills of senior high school learners and promote parental involvement, the following activities are recommended as part of the intervention program:

- **Parent-Teacher Conferences:** Regular conferences should be organized to facilitate discussions between parents and teachers, allowing them to share insights, discuss students' progress, and establish collaborative goals.
- **Parent and Student Workshops:** Workshops should be conducted to educate parents and students on effective literacy strategies, creating a supportive home literacy environment, and fostering positive reading and writing habits.
- **Reading Programs:** Structured reading programs should be implemented to encourage regular reading activities between students and parents, such as shared reading sessions and book clubs.
- **Writing Prompts:** Providing writing prompts and activities that promote creative expression, critical thinking, and effective written communication skills.
- **Online Resources:** Curating online resources and platforms that offer a wide range of reading materials, interactive exercises, and language practice activities accessible to both parents and students.

- **Home-School Communication:** Establishing effective communication channels between parents and teachers, such as regular updates, newsletters, and digital platforms, to keep parents informed about students' literacy progress and provide support materials.
- **Parental Involvement:** Encouraging parents to actively participate in their children's literacy development by providing guidance, support, and creating a positive learning environment at home.
- **Assessment and Evaluation:** Implementing regular assessments and evaluations to monitor students' literacy progress and identify areas that require further attention and support.

Additionally, the following activities are recommended to further enhance the intervention program:

- **Parent and Teacher Orientation:** Conducting orientations to familiarize parents and teachers with the goals, strategies, and expectations of the intervention program.
- **Home Literacy Kits:** Providing families with literacy kits containing books, educational resources, and instructional materials to support literacy activities at home.
- **Literacy Workshops:** Organizing workshops for parents to enhance their understanding of literacy development, effective reading strategies, and techniques to promote language skills.
- **Parent-Child Reading Programs:** Facilitating programs that encourage parents and children to read together, fostering a love for reading and strengthening the parent-child bond.
- **Online Learning Platforms:** Expanding the use of online learning platforms that provide interactive and engaging literacy activities, allowing for flexible and independent learning opportunities.

It is crucial to allocate the necessary resources for each activity, including venue rental, snacks, honorariums for speakers or facilitators, printing and packaging materials, workshop materials, reading materials, guides, and incentives to encourage active parent participation. These resources will ensure the successful implementation and sustainability of the intervention program, leading to improved home literacy skills and increased parental involvement (Epstein & Sanders, 2006; Posey-Maddox & Haley-Lock, 2020).

In summary, incorporating parental involvement and enhancing home literacy skills can significantly impact students' educational outcomes. By strengthening the school, teacher, and parent relationship, expanding the scope of parent interaction, and implementing the proposed intervention program, educational policies and practices can be improved to create a more supportive and nurturing learning environment for students. This holistic approach, supported by evidence-based strategies and resources, can contribute to students' academic success and overall development.

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